

MASTER'S THESIS

*Development of a Seakeeping Tool
for Wind-Assisted Vessels*

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August 19, 2025

Acknowledgements

I would like to sincerely thank VPLP Design for giving me the opportunity to work on such interesting and challenging topics. These six months have been both rigorous and immensely rewarding.

My heartfelt thanks go to the VPLP Nantes team, whose support throughout this period has been invaluable. I am deeply grateful to Paul, who has been a constant source of ideas and guidance, and an excellent mentor.

I would like to thank Diego, João, and Ceci, who made my time in Nantes so much more enjoyable outside of work.

A special word of gratitude goes to my parents, whose unwavering support during my entire master's at Centrale has been a continuous source of motivation.

Finally, I would like to thank my girlfriend, for being by my side every step of the way, and especially for her encouragement and patience during the final stages of writing this manuscript.

Harishankar Sivaprasad
Nantes, August 2025

Abstract

This work presents the development of the frequency-domain sea-keeping tool *sea-keepy*, with a focus on extending its capabilities. Key contributions include the implementation of forward-speed effects, a frequency-domain slamming subroutine, a non-potential roll-damping module, and an aerodynamic damping model to quantify the motion-damping effects of wing-assisted propulsion (WAP) devices.

A frequency-domain slamming formulation was implemented and shown to offer improvements over the existing time-series method, with qualitative validation demonstrating its potential.

The roll-damping subpackage was implemented using Ikeda's component-based approach, enabling the inclusion of non-potential roll-damping effects.

An aerodynamic damping model was implemented to efficiently evaluate the damping contributions of Wind Assisted Propulsion (WAP) devices. Finally, a case study on a KVLCC2 tanker equipped with rigid wing sails demonstrated reductions in motion amplitudes, especially in beam seas, with increasing benefits in more severe sea states.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Seakeeping broadly refers to the study of a vessel's motions and responses when subjected to wave action. In ship design, predicting how a floating structure behaves in waves through model testing, computational simulations, or analytical calculations are essential to ensuring both safety and performance.

Historically, formal seakeeping analyses have primarily focused on large commercial and naval vessels, where even moderate improvements in dynamic behavior can yield significant economic or operational benefits. In contrast, the design of small pleasure craft and yachts has traditionally relied more on empirical methods, designer intuition, and feedback from sea trials, rather than systematic computational analysis [1].

Figure 1.1: Artists' impression of the cargo carrying trimaran VELA [5] (*Nicolas Gagnon & Johan Ong*)

Regulatory frameworks for small craft have similarly emphasized static stability over dynamic behavior. For instance, the ISO-12217 standard series, *Small Craft: Stability and Buoyancy*, prescribes procedures for assessing a vessel's intact stability and reserve buoyancy, assigning a design category (A/B/C/D) based primarily on static righting ability and downflooding resistance [2]. Dynamic responses to

waves such as motions and accelerations that influence onboard comfort and safety are not directly addressed within these criteria. As a result, safety certification for recreational yachts remains governed predominantly by buoyancy and static stability requirements.

As a result of the factors discussed above, a dedicated seakeeping analysis tool had not previously been necessary within VPLP Design [3]. Traditional design approaches, grounded in empirical knowledge and accumulated experience, were sufficient for the firm’s typical projects. However, with the development of larger, ocean-capable maritime vessels, notably *Persévérance* (2022) [4] and *VELA* (2023) [5], the need for more systematic and predictive seakeeping evaluations became increasingly evident.

Within VPLP’s racing yacht division, however, a weakly nonlinear seakeeping tool had already been developed, as described by Kerdraon et al. [6]. This six-degree-of-freedom Dynamic Velocity Prediction Program (DVPP) models hydrodynamic loads on the hull and appendages, as well as aerodynamic forces on the rig, and also accounts for forward speed effects. Higher-fidelity, time-domain simulations of this type are indispensable for optimizing the performance and safety of offshore racing yachts, where dynamic loads are a critical design consideration.

Nevertheless, for more conventional maritime projects and for preliminary design phases, this level of computational complexity is often inefficient and unnecessarily resource-intensive. Consequently, a new linear, frequency-domain seakeeping analysis tool, *seakeepy*, was developed to provide faster, more practical predictions of vessel motions in both regular and irregular waves.

Figure 1.2: Schematic of different modules in *seakeepy* (VPLP Design)

This code leverages some components of the earlier nonlinear codebase, offering a robust initial platform for development. However, substantial work remains to fully extend its capabilities, and this will be the scope of the present study.

1.1 *seakeepy*

seakeepy was designed as a Python package with multiple submodules, following a modular structure that can be adapted to a variety of projects. This design allows engineers to build custom notebooks tailored to specific project requirements. Figure 1.2 illustrates the different modules within *Seakeepy*. Table 1.1 describes their functions.

Table 1.1: Overview of *Seakeepy* subpackages

Subpackage	Description
<i>Rad/Diff</i>	Contains tools to invoke NEMOH (Babarit and Delhommeau [7]) for the calculation of radiation and diffraction coefficients.
<i>Hydrostatics</i>	Handles routine hydrostatic calculations for a vessel, including the computation of the stiffness matrix for RAO calculations.
<i>Inertia</i>	Computes the vessel's inertia matrix.
<i>Spectrum</i>	Deals with the wave spectrum and related calculations.
<i>Seakeeping</i>	Contains a range of submodules and routines for extensive regulatory and criteria checks.

The further development of the *Seakeeping* subpackage, along with associated improvements in other related subpackages, will be the main focus of the present work.

1.2 Objectives

At the outset of this work, *seakeepy* lacked several key functionalities present in state-of-the-art linear seakeeping tools. The primary objective was therefore to enhance the package to bridge this gap, focusing on both computational efficiency and modelling accuracy. The specific objectives were as follows:

1. **Forward speed capability:** Implement the analysis of vessels operating with forward speed by introducing the concepts of encounter frequency and encounter spectrum into the code, alongside modifications to the RAO calculation routines.
2. **Improve slamming analysis:** Address the limitations of the existing slamming analysis subpackage (discussed in later sections) by developing a new frequency-domain slamming analysis module.

3. **Roll damping improvements:** Implement an additional roll damping subpackage to account for non-potential roll damping effects, enabling more accurate estimation of roll responses.
4. **Wind-assisted propulsion effects:** Develop an aerodynamic damping subpackage to quantify the motion damping effects of wind-assisted propulsion (WAP) devices.

The theoretical background and implementation details of these developments are presented in the subsequent sections of this work.

Chapter 2

Background and Theory

This chapter presents the theoretical framework and technical background underlying the development of *seakeepy*. It begins by outlining the fundamental principles of frequency-domain seakeeping analysis, establishing a foundation for understanding vessel responses to wave-induced motions. The discussion then explores slamming, additional roll damping, and the motion-damping effects of assistive wind propulsion devices. Overall, the chapter provides a comprehensive reference to support future research and the continued development of the program.

2.1 Linear Seakeeping Theory

As the name suggests, the wave description presented below correspond to the so-called *first-order wave theory*, or *linear wave theory*. Linearity arises from the Laplace equation together with the boundary conditions considered: the principle of superposition holds for the velocity potentials and, consequently, for the surface elevation, wave loads and vessel responses.

The *linear seakeeping theory of ship motion* is based on three essential assumptions:

- The sea surface elevation is assumed to be a realization of an ergodic Gaussian stochastic process with zero mean. Thus, the process is entirely described by its power spectral density - the sea spectrum.
- The wave-excitation loads and ship motion responses are assumed to be linear.
- The ship keeps a steady course and moves at a constant average speed.

2.1.1 Coordinate Systems

The motion of a ship in a seaway is complex and requires a well-defined coordinate system to describe its six degrees of freedom (6DOF). These degrees of freedom consist of three translational movements (surge, sway, and heave) and three rotational movements (roll, pitch, and yaw). To accurately model these motions, 3 primary reference frames are used: an earth-fixed frame, an inertial frame, and a body-fixed frame. This work follows the sign conventions of the NEMOH code (Babarit and Delhommeau [7]) as shown in Figure 2.1

Figure 2.1: Primary reference frames and sign conventions.

$OeXeYeZe$ is the Earth-fixed coordinate system, with the X_eY_e -plane on the calm water surface and the Z_e -axis positive upwards.

$OXYZ$ is an inertial coordinate system moving with the steady forward speed of the body. The XY -plane coincides with the X_eY_e -plane, and the Z -axis is parallel to the Z_e -axis.

$oxyz$ is a body-fixed coordinate system that moves not only with the steady forward speed but also with the unsteady rigid-body motions of the body. The z -axis passes through the center of gravity (COG). When the body has no unsteady motions, $oxyz$ coincides with $OXYZ$, with the origin located on the mean free surface.

2.1.2 Encounter Frequency

When the ship is at zero speed, the frequency of wave excitation coincides with the wave frequency ω . However, once the ship is in motion, the frequency perceived on board differs from the actual wave frequency. This shifted frequency is referred to as the *encounter frequency*, denoted by ω_e .

For a ship advancing with an average speed U , it is more convenient to describe the sea relative to a coordinate system ($OXYZ$) that moves with the vessel's mean forward speed, as illustrated in Figure 2.3. We can express the encounter frequency as:

$$\omega_e = \omega - \frac{\omega^2 U}{g} \cos \beta \quad (2.1)$$

Figure 2.2: Wave heading angle definition and sign conventions.

where U is ship speed and β is wave heading angle.

2.1.3 Equations of Motion

For simulating ship motions in a seaway, the ship is considered as a rigid body, with elastic deformations of the hull assumed negligible. Newton's second law governs the motion in six degrees of freedom (6DOF) as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^6 [(M_{jk} + A_{jk})\ddot{\eta}_k + B_{jk}\dot{\eta}_k + C_{jk}\eta_k] = F_j(t) \quad (2.2)$$

The variables in Equation 2.2 represent the complete coupled dynamics of the ship motion system. The displacement components η_1 , η_2 , and η_3 correspond to the translational motions in surge (longitudinal), sway (transverse), and heave (vertical) directions respectively, while η_4 , η_5 , and η_6 describe the rotational motions of roll (about longitudinal axis), pitch (about transverse axis), and yaw (about vertical axis). The mass matrix components M_{jk} contain both the vessel's rigid-body mass properties and mass moments of inertia, forming the conventional inertia terms in Newton's equations.

The frequency-dependent added mass coefficients $A_{jk}(\omega)$ account for the additional inertia caused by the surrounding water that must be accelerated with the ship's motion, representing the hydrodynamic contribution to the system's inertia. Hydrodynamic damping effects, which capture the energy dissipation through wave radiation and viscous effects, are contained in the coefficients $B_{jk}(\omega)$. The hydrostatic restoring coefficients C_{jk} model the buoyancy forces and moments

that tend to return the ship to its equilibrium position, particularly important for heave, roll and pitch motions.

Finally, $F_j(t)$ represents the wave excitation forces and moments imposed on the vessel by the seaway, encompassing both the Froude-Krilov and diffraction components of wave action on the hull.

With the assumption of linear theory and steady state response, the frequency-domain representation of the system is:

$$\sum_{k=1}^6 [(M_{jk} + A_{jk}(\omega_e))\ddot{\eta}_k + B_{jk}(\omega_e)\dot{\eta}_k + C_{jk}\eta_k] = F_j e^{i\omega_e t} \quad (2.3)$$

seakeepy can calculate the hydrostatic restoring coefficients using the vessel geometry. The frequency-domain hydrodynamic coefficients and wave excitation forces are obtained using boundary element methods, with NEMOH serving as the computational tool in this study .

2.1.4 Response Amplitude Operator (RAO)

The Response Amplitude Operator (RAO) is a fundamental concept in seakeeping analysis that quantifies vessel response in a given sea state. Mathematically, the RAO describes the ratio of ship motion amplitude to wave amplitude, expressed as:

$$\text{RAO}(\omega, \beta) = \left| \frac{\eta_a}{\zeta_a} \right| \quad (2.4)$$

where η_a represents the amplitude of ship motion in a particular degree of freedom and ζ_a is the incident wave amplitude. While closely related to transfer functions, the RAO specifically refers to the magnitude of the response without encompassing phase information.

The excitation loads F_j in the equations of motion are complex amplitudes. For regular waves with frequency ω and direction β , these loads can be expressed through the linear relation:

$$F_j e^{-i\omega_e t} = \zeta_a X_j(\omega, \beta) e^{-i\omega_e t} \quad (2.5)$$

where $X_j(\omega, \beta)$ represents the complex-valued function for excitation loads of unit amplitude.

It is crucial to note that the ship responds to wave excitation loads at the *encounter frequency* ω_e , which means the hydrodynamic coefficients (added mass A_{jk} and damping B_{jk}) must be evaluated at this encounter frequency.

However, the wave excitation forces F_j fundamentally act on the vessel at the wave frequency ω of the seaway. While temporally perceived by the moving vessel at ω_e due to the Doppler effect, the spatial distribution of wave loads remains governed by ω . The changes in the diffraction force due to forward speed have not been investigated and are assumed to be unchanged in this work.

Using the complex notation for body motions:

$$\eta_k = \eta_{ka} e^{-i\omega_e t} \quad (2.6)$$

and substituting into the equations of motion (2.3), we obtain the frequency-domain solution:

$$\sum_{k=1}^6 \left[-\omega_e^2 (M_{jk} + A_{jk}(\omega_e)) + i\omega_e B_{jk}(\omega_e) + C_{jk} \right] \eta_{ka} = \zeta_a X_j(\omega, \beta) \quad (2.7)$$

The transfer function relating wave amplitude to body motions is then derived as:

$$H(\omega_e, \beta) = \frac{\eta_a}{\zeta_a} = \left[-\omega_e^2 (\mathbf{M} + \mathbf{A}(\omega_e)) + i\omega_e \mathbf{B}(\omega_e) + \mathbf{C} \right]^{-1} \mathbf{X}(\omega, \beta) \quad (2.8)$$

where the RAO corresponds to the modulus of this complex transfer function:

$$\text{RAO}(\omega_e, \beta) = |H(\omega_e, \beta)| \quad (2.9)$$

2.1.5 Irregular Wave Representation

For engineering applications, the irregular sea surface is typically modeled as a stationary Gaussian random process. The instantaneous wave elevation can be expressed as

$$\zeta(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N a_n \cos(\omega_n t + \varepsilon_n), \quad (2.10)$$

where a_n is the amplitude of component n , ω_n its angular frequency, and ε_n a random phase angle uniformly distributed between 0 and 2π . This discrete formulation converges to a continuous spectral description as $N \rightarrow \infty$ and $\Delta\omega \rightarrow 0$.

2.1.6 Wave Energy Spectrum

A convenient way to describe an irregular seaway is through the *wave energy spectrum*, which represents how the total energy is distributed among different

wave frequencies. The spectral density $S(\omega)$ is plotted as a function of angular frequency ω , with the vertical axis showing the spectral ordinate. The area under the curve between two frequencies corresponds to the energy contained in that frequency band.

Figure 2.3: Connection between frequency-domain and time-domain representation of waves in a long-crested short-term sea state (*Faltinsen [8]*).

For a discrete frequency component at ω_n , the variance of the corresponding wave elevation is related to the spectral density by

$$S(\omega_n) = \frac{a_n^2}{2 \Delta\omega}, \quad (2.11)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ is the frequency spacing. The total variance of the surface elevation, and hence the total wave energy, is obtained by integrating the spectrum:

$$m_0 = \int_0^\infty S(\omega) d\omega. \quad (2.12)$$

It is often useful to connect this to the *significant wave height*, which is defined as

$$H_s = 4\sqrt{m_0}. \quad (2.13)$$

Finally, to reconstruct a time history of the irregular sea surface from a given spectrum as given by 2.10, we choose the wave amplitudes as:

$$a_n = \sqrt{2S(\omega_n) \Delta\omega}, \quad (2.14)$$

and random phases $\varepsilon_n \sim [0, 2\pi]$. While the reconstructed signal will not match the exact original realization of the sea state, it preserves the same statistical properties and spectral energy distribution.

In practice, standardized wave spectra derived from experimental data are used to approximate the sea state, utilizing statistical parameters such as the significant wave height H_s and the peak wave period T_p , obtained from weather forecasts or hindcasts. If wind-waves or swells dominate the sea state, a one-peaked spectrum such as the Joint North Sea Wave Project (JONSWAP) spectrum or the Pierson–Moskowitz (PM) spectrum is typically chosen. When low-frequency swells significantly influence the high-frequency wind-waves, a bimodal spectrum like the Ochi-Hubble spectrum can be used to account for the individual contributions to the total wave energy.

2.1.7 Encounter Spectrum

The wave energy spectrum $S(\omega)$, as introduced earlier, describes the distribution of wave energy as observed at a fixed point in the ocean. However, a moving ship does not experience the same spectrum. Instead, it encounters waves at encounter frequencies due to its forward speed as explained in section 2.1.2. This leads to the definition of the *encounter spectrum*, which represents the wave energy as perceived in the ship's reference frame.

Figure 2.4: Transformation from the wave energy spectrum (top) to the encounter spectrum (bottom). The shaded areas illustrate how equal energy is preserved when shifting from wave frequency ω to encounter frequency ω_e . (Lloyd [9])

To ensure energy conservation, the spectral ordinates must transform in such a way that the energy contained in a given frequency interval in the wave spectrum

equals the energy in the corresponding interval in the encounter spectrum. This is illustrated by Fig. 2.4. Mathematically, this condition is expressed as

$$S(\omega_e) \Delta\omega_e = S(\omega) \Delta\omega. \quad (2.15)$$

From this relationship, the encounter spectrum is obtained as

$$S(\omega_e) = S(\omega) \frac{d\omega}{d\omega_e}. \quad (2.16)$$

Substituting the transformation for ω_e gives

$$S(\omega_e) = S(\omega) \frac{g}{g - 2\omega U \cos \beta}. \quad (2.17)$$

In the case of a head sea ($\mu = 180^\circ$), the energy is spread out over a wider band of higher frequencies than for a stationary point spectrum. Whereas, for a following sea, at moderate speeds, energy tends to be concentrated in narrower bands at low frequencies, with the spectral density becoming infinite at a point. This singularity in the spectral density is integrable, so that the energy in any given band of frequencies is finite.

The following sea spectra are double-valued in the range of frequencies for which it is possible to encounter waves of two wavelengths at the same frequency of encounter. Additionally, these spectra extend into the ‘negative frequency’ range. The physical interpretation of ‘negative frequency’ for the following seas is merely that the waves are being overtaken by the vessel (Bhattacharyya [10]).

2.1.8 Response Spectrum

The *response spectrum* represents the transformation of wave energy into the response energy of a vessel in the frequency domain. It is calculated as the product of the wave energy spectra at each encounter frequency and the square of the ship transfer function at the same encounter frequency as illustrated by Fig. 2.6. Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$S_{xx}(\omega_e) = |H(\omega_e)|^2 S(\omega_e) \quad (2.18)$$

The same techniques used for the wave spectra can be applied to determine the RMS values of velocity, acceleration, and motions from the response spectrum using spectral moments. The n -th order spectral moment is defined as:

$$m_n = \int_0^\infty \omega_e^n S_{xx}(\omega_e) d\omega_e \quad (2.19)$$

The root-mean-square (RMS) values of motion quantities are obtained from the spectral moments as:

$$\text{RMS motion amplitude: } a_0 = \sqrt{m_0} \tag{2.20}$$

$$\text{RMS velocity: } a_1 = \sqrt{m_2} \tag{2.21}$$

$$\text{RMS acceleration: } a_2 = \sqrt{m_4} \tag{2.22}$$

Figure 2.5: Energy spectra and response of a ship in an irregular sea (illustrated for heave). (Molland [11])

Thus, by computing the spectral moments of the response spectrum, one can estimate the expected amplitude, velocity, and acceleration of ship motions due to waves.

2.2 Slamming of Vessels

Ship slamming is one of the most significant secondary loads affecting vessel structures, particularly in rough seas. It occurs when the vessel's forefoot (most commonly) or another submerged part of the hull emerges from the water due to the combined effects of pitching, heaving, and rolling, and it re-enters with a high vertical relative velocity. This re-entry generates transient, impulsive loads that could even lead to substantial structural damage.

Figure 2.6: A small vessel experiencing hull bottom slamming in rough seas. (*Ben Salter*)

This section examines the fundamental aspects of slamming, including its occurrence conditions and influencing factors, followed by a discussion of the mathematical modeling of the phenomenon.

2.2.1 Fundamentals of Slamming Phenomenon

Slamming is characterised by extreme transient loadings which occur when a vessel's bottom hull structure impacts the water surface after emerging due to wave action. This phenomenon results in the transmission of potential energy from the local wave to the vessel structure at the impact moment, concentrated in a relatively small reference area. These impulsive loads are particularly severe, rising to extremely high pressures for very short durations, typically just milliseconds, with the highest pressure experienced at the center of the impact area and decreasing outward.

The significance of slamming lies in its potential to cause both local and global structural effects. Locally, it can result in plastic deformation of the bottom structure in the slam reference area, while globally, it may induce vibration throughout the entire hull structure, a phenomenon known as *whipping*. Faulkner et al [12].

identified slamming as a constant source of hull cracking in the forward void spaces of fast multi-hull vessels, highlighting its critical importance in vessel structural integrity.

Conditions Required for Slamming Occurrence

Szebehely [13] and Ochi [14] found through tests in regular wave conditions that slamming typically occurs when the ship's hull and the water surface are nearly parallel during impact. Szebehely identified several essential conditions for slamming to occur:

- The emergence of the bow from the water,
- A sufficient magnitude of relative velocity between the bow and the wave surface,
- An unfavourable phase relationship between the vessel's motion and the wave movement.

Threshold Velocity

Ochi and Motter [15], through tests in irregular waves confirmed that bow emergence is a prerequisite but not a sufficient cause for slamming. Their research concluded that slamming produces significant stresses only when the impact velocity exceeds a certain magnitude—the threshold velocity. Based on Froude scale law, they established the following expression:

$$v_t = 0.096\sqrt{gL}$$

where L is the ship length (in meters) and $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$.

This concept provides a practical criterion for determining when slamming events are likely to cause significant structural responses.

2.2.2 Factors Influencing Slamming

Sea State

Model test results analyzed by Ochi [15] demonstrate that slamming severity increases with wave severity when other conditions remain constant.

Speed Effects

Forward speed significantly affects slamming severity. Increasing speed raises both the probability of slamming and the magnitude of impact pressures (Ochi [15]). Additionally, the location of maximum pressure tends to shift aft. However, impact pressures may decrease above supercritical speeds due to reduced ship motions. A common rule is to reduce speed if slamming occurs in more than 3 out of 100 passing waves. This was further confirmed by the Nordforsk study [16], which puts the acceptable probability of slamming for merchant ships at 0.03

Heading Angle

Model tests by Ochi [15] showed that the most severe slamming occurs when waves approach from directly ahead or up to 30 degrees off the bow. This can be attributed to the fact that pitch and heave, the major contributors to the relative motion between wave and ship, are maximum for this range of headings. Beyond 60 degrees, slamming becomes negligible.

Draft Influence

Increasing draft reduces the frequency and magnitude of slamming impacts (Ochi [15]), primarily due to less frequent forefoot emergence. This makes higher drafts advantageous in minimizing structural damage from slamming.

2.2.3 Slamming Analysis in Irregular Seas

Slamming criteria checks are an essential part of the early design process, and it was therefore necessary for *seakeepy* to include this capability. A time-domain and a frequency-domain approach for slamming analysis are discussed below.

2.2.4 Time Domain Analysis

Slamming events in irregular seas can be analyzed in the time domain if the transfer functions for relative motion are known. These events are typically identified using the emergence criteria and the threshold velocity concept.

For a vessel moving at a forward speed U with wave heading angle β , the free surface elevation in the Earth-fixed coordinate system is given by:

$$\eta(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n A_i \cos(-\omega_i t + k_i U t \cos(\beta) + \phi_i) \quad (2.23)$$

The corresponding vertical motion of the vessel is expressed as:

$$z(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n B_i \cos(-\omega_i t + k_i U t \cos(\beta) + \phi_i + \varphi(\omega_{e,i})) \quad (2.24)$$

Here ϕ_i are random phase angles and $\varphi(\omega_{e,i})$ are the phase angles of the vessel transfer function corresponding to the encounter frequencies $\omega_{e,i}$. The wave and vessel response amplitudes are:

$$A_i = \sqrt{2S(\omega_{e,i}) \Delta\omega} \quad (2.25)$$

$$B_i = \sqrt{2S(\omega_{e,i}) |H(\omega_{e,i})|^2 \Delta\omega} \quad (2.26)$$

The relative vertical motion at a sectional depth d is then:

$$z_{\text{rel}}(t) = z(t) - \eta(t) - d \quad (2.27)$$

Slamming is detected by identifying zero-down crossings of the relative motion and checking whether the vertical velocity exceeds the critical threshold.

The computational cost of time-domain analysis can be substantial, particularly when multiple sea states and wave headings need to be considered. Moreover, the choice of time discretization can significantly influence the results, introducing artifacts that should ideally not affect the analysis.

For instance, slamming criteria are often quantified in terms of slamming probabilities. In a time-domain approach, these probabilities are typically estimated as the ratio of the total duration of slamming events to the total simulation time. However, the dynamics of slamming are not captured by linear seakeeping theory. As a result, the estimated durations of slamming events depend almost entirely on the time discretization, which can lead to inaccurate or misleading results.

Additionally, there is a fundamental physical inconsistency inherent in the assumptions of linear seakeeping theory. Specifically, the theory assumes that the ship remains at a fixed vertical level ($z = 0$) regardless of the wave amplitude. This assumption becomes increasingly invalid as wave amplitudes grow, and it can further contribute to inaccuracies in the analysis.

2.2.5 Frequency Domain Analysis

Ochi and Motter [15] proposed a frequency-domain probabilistic model, assuming the independence of relative displacement and relative velocity. A slam is considered to occur when both the relative motion amplitude exceeds the draft and the relative velocity exceed a critical threshold.

Assuming slams follow a Poisson process, the probability of a slam per wave cycle is given by:

$$P_{\text{slam}} = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{d^2}{2\sigma_d^2} + \frac{v_c^2}{2\sigma_v^2}\right)\right) \quad (2.28)$$

where d is the draft of the vessel at the considered section and v_c is the critical velocity threshold. σ_d^2 and σ_v^2 are variances (spectral moments) of relative displacement and relative velocity, respectively.

A more intuitive way to assess slamming is to estimate the number of probable slamming events within a given duration (in seconds), expressed as:

$$N_{\text{slam}} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_v^2}{\sigma_d^2}} P_{\text{slam}} \quad (2.29)$$

Relative Vertical Transfer Functions

The relative vertical transfer function, as the name suggests, is the transfer function of a vessel at a given point relative to a wave of unit amplitude in the vertical (heave) direction. This can be thought of as a frequency domain equivalent of Eq. 2.27.

To obtain the vertical transfer function for a vessel at a point x considering heave and pitch, the transfer functions can be superimposed geometrically since they are linear as:

$$H_z(\omega_e) = H_3(\omega_e) - xH_5(\omega_e) \quad (2.30)$$

where $H_3(\omega_e)$ and $H_5(\omega_e)$ are the heave, pitch transfer functions, respectively.

The relative vertical transfer function is then given by:

$$H_r(\omega_e) = H_z(\omega_e) - e^{i\frac{\omega_e^2 x}{g}} \quad (2.31)$$

Here, the exponential term accounts for the phase shift of the incident wave at location x . Note that while the transfer functions are functions of the encounter frequency ω_e , the exponential term representing the wave elevation remains a function of the wave frequency ω . This is because the waveform does not vary spatially, and the waves are experienced by the vessel only temporally at the encounter frequency.

Two-Dimensional Positioning and Heading Effects

To incorporate the effects of roll (which is particularly important for multihull vessels) and wave heading β , the vertical transfer function at point (x, y) is extended as:

$$H_z(\omega_e) = H_3(\omega_e) - xH_5(\omega_e) + yH_4(\omega_e) \quad (2.32)$$

where $H_4(\omega_e)$ is the roll transfer function. The corresponding relative vertical transfer function becomes:

$$H_r(\omega_e) = H_z(\omega_e) - e^{i(kx \cos \beta + ky \sin \beta)} \quad (2.33)$$

with $k = \omega^2/g$, the wave number.

Spectral Moments for Slamming Prediction

The spectral moments of relative displacement and relative velocity, required for estimating slamming probability, are computed as:

$$\sigma_d^2 = \int_0^\infty S(\omega_e) |H_r(\omega_e)|^2 d\omega_e, \quad (2.34)$$

$$\sigma_v^2 = \int_0^\infty S(\omega_e) |i\omega_e H_r(\omega_e)|^2 d\omega_e, \quad (2.35)$$

where $S(\omega_e)$ is the encounter spectrum and $|H_r(\omega_e)|$ is the relative motion response amplitude operator (RAO). These integrals account for the sea state via the encounter spectrum and represent the variances of the relative displacement and relative velocity response spectra, respectively.

2.3 Additional Roll Damping

Roll motion is one of the most critical yet least understood motions experienced by ships and offshore structures. Among the six degrees of freedom, rolling poses a significant threat due to its potential to induce large amplitudes, leading to cargo shifting or even capsizing. This is primarily because both the roll restoring moment and damping exhibit strong nonlinear characteristics. While linear diffraction and radiation theories are typically sufficient to predict the motion of large floating structures in most degrees of freedom, they often fall short in accurately capturing roll behavior, particularly for long structures such as ships, barges, and long offshore platforms (Chakrabarti [18]). For these structures, the radiation damping component is minimal compared to the total damping, and their natural roll periods often coincide with the frequency range of dominant wave energy, leading to dynamic amplification.

Consequently, obtaining a reliable estimate of roll damping is essential, albeit challenging, due to the nonlinear nature of the phenomenon. This section explores the components of roll damping and their empirical estimation.

2.3.1 Roll Damping Estimation Methods

During the 1950s and 1960s, pioneering scientific investigations into the individual physical aspects of roll damping were undertaken. These studies laid the groundwork for understanding the mechanisms behind ship roll damping. A major advancement came in the late 1970s with the development of the component-based method by Ikeda, Himeno, and Tanaka, all of Osaka Prefecture University (Ikeda et al. [20] [21], [22]; Himeno [25]). This semi-empirical approach decomposed total roll damping into several physically distinct components: wave-making, hull friction, eddy-making, lift forces, and bilge keel effects. By analyzing each component separately and summing them linearly, this method provided a practical and relatively accurate way to estimate roll damping for conventional hull forms at small roll angles and both zero and forward speeds. It became the first comprehensive model to systematically incorporate multiple physical phenomena into roll damping prediction.

Since its introduction, the component-based approach has remained the state-of-the-art in frequency domain roll damping estimation. It has also been extended to more complex configurations such as multihull vessels (Katayama et al. [26]), where the same principles are adapted to account for the interactions between hulls. While initially developed for small-amplitude motions (typically up to 10 degrees), ongoing research continues to refine and expand the model to cover a broader range of conditions and hull geometries.

2.3.2 Equation of Ship Roll Motion

While the other degrees of motion of a ship, barge, or semisubmersible may be described reasonably well by linear equations, this is not the case for roll motion. The equation of motion in roll can be expressed in general as:

$$(I + A_{44})\ddot{\phi} + B(\dot{\phi}) + C(\phi) = M \cos(\omega t) \quad (2.36)$$

where ϕ is the angular roll displacement, I is the total moment of inertia in roll, A_{44} is the frequency dependent roll added mass, $B(\dot{\phi})$ is the roll damping term. $C(\phi, t)$ is the restoring moment (which may be nonlinear) and M is the wave exciting moment.

Roll damping coefficients can be expressed in various forms, including linear and nonlinear representations. A common nonlinear representation of the damping coefficient $B(\dot{\phi})$ is a power series expansion in $\dot{\phi}$ and $|\dot{\phi}|$:

$$B(\dot{\phi}) = B_1\dot{\phi} + B_2\dot{\phi}|\dot{\phi}| + B_3\dot{\phi}^3 + \dots \quad (2.37)$$

Here, B_1 [$\text{N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}$], B_2 [$\text{N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^2$], B_3 [$\text{N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^3$], etc., are the nonlinear damping coefficients, which are considered constants during steady periodic oscillation, characterized by steady rolling amplitude ϕ_a and frequency ω_R .

2.3.3 Equivalent Linearization Techniques

In practice, the total damping is often approximated by an equivalent linear damping term:

$$B(\dot{\phi}) \approx B_{eq}\dot{\phi} \quad (2.38)$$

The calculation of the equivalent linear damping coefficient B_{eq} has to be handled differently in the case of regular waves and irregular waves. Both these methods are discussed below.

Regular Waves

The equivalent linear damping coefficient B_{eq} is typically determined by equating the energy dissipated over one half-cycle of motion for both the nonlinear and linear damping cases.

$$\int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\omega_R}} B_{eq} \dot{\phi}^2 dt = \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{\omega_R}} B(\dot{\phi}) \dot{\phi} dt \quad (2.39)$$

where the roll velocity is assumed to be harmonic:

$$\dot{\phi}(t) = \phi_a \omega_R \sin(\omega_R t) \quad (2.40)$$

This yields the expression:

$$B_{eq} = B_1 + \frac{8}{3\pi} B_2 \omega_R \phi_a + \frac{3}{4} B_3 (\omega_R \phi_a)^2 \quad (2.41)$$

Irregular Waves

Irregular waves can be represented as the superposition of regular waves with different periods, amplitudes, and phases. When incident waves are modeled as a random process, the resulting excitation force F_x becomes a random process as well, and consequently, so does the roll motion $\phi(t)$.

For irregular roll motion analysis, we require a specialized approach to linearize the roll damping term. This method is known as *stochastic linearization*. The fundamental assumption of this technique is that the difference between the damping for the linearized term and the actual nonlinear value can be minimized using the least squares method. The final expression of the equivalent linear damping coefficient is given by:

$$B_{eq} = B_1 + \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi}} B_2 \sigma_{\dot{x}} + 3B_3 \sigma_{\dot{x}}^2 \quad (2.42)$$

where $\sigma_{\dot{x}}$ is the standard deviation of the roll velocity response. The complete derivation of this expression can be found in Yamanouchi [28]

2.3.4 Ikeda's Method

The equivalent linear damping coefficient B_{eq} is commonly assumed to be composed of five additive components:

$$B_{eq} = B_W + B_F + B_E + B_L + B_{BK} \quad (2.43)$$

It is assumed that the interaction between these components is negligible, allowing them to be summed linearly. Each damping component may be expressed for both

the zero-speed and forward-speed cases. In the following sections, subscript 0 is added to denote the zero-speed condition, for example, B_{W0} or B_{L0} .

The wave and lift damping components (B_W and B_L) are linear with respect to the roll angular velocity $\dot{\phi}$. In contrast, the frictional, eddy, and appendage-related damping components (B_F , B_E , and B_{BK}) exhibit nonlinear behaviour, especially at larger roll amplitudes.

2.3.5 Wave Making Component

The wave making (B_W) component accounts for between 5% and 30% of the roll damping for a general-cargo type ship. However, the component may have a larger effect for ships with a shallow draught and wide section (Ikeda et al.[21]). It is typically calculated using potential flow radiation-diffraction computational methods and is considered more accurate than the empirical formula from Ikeda (Falzarano et al. [29]).

2.3.6 Friction Component

Frictional damping arises due to the viscous skin friction stresses acting on the hull surface as the ship undergoes roll motion. This component is influenced by both the hull geometry and the nature of the flow, laminar at model scale, and turbulent at full scale. It is also affected marginally by the presence of bilge keels and forward speed.

Experimental results by Ikeda et al. [21] show that the frictional damping contributes about 8 – 10% of the total roll damping for a 2 m long model ship and about 1 – 3% for full-scale ships due to Reynolds number scaling effects.

Other components such as wave, eddy, and bilge keel damping are less sensitive to scale, allowing the use of non-dimensional coefficients across model and full scale. However, the frictional component must be treated separately when scaling.

Zero-Speed, Laminar Flow Case

Kato [19] provided a semi-empirical formula for the skin friction damping coefficient under laminar conditions and zero forward speed:

$$B_{F0} = \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho S r_e^3 \phi_a \omega C_f \quad (2.44)$$

The friction coefficient C_f is defined as:

$$C_f = 1.328 \sqrt{\frac{2\pi\nu}{3.22r_e^2\phi_a^2\omega}} \quad (2.45)$$

The effective bilge radius r_e is estimated using:

$$r_e = \frac{1}{\pi} [(0.887 + 0.145C_B)(1.7D + C_B B) - 2OG] \quad (2.46)$$

And the wetted surface area S is approximated empirically by:

$$S = L(1.7D + C_B B) \quad (2.47)$$

Here ρ is the fluid density, ϕ_a is the roll amplitude (radians), ω is the roll frequency. ν is the kinematic viscosity. L , B , D are the ship length, breadth, and draft, and OG is the vertical distance from roll axis to center of gravity, taken positive downwards.

Turbulent Flow Correction

At full scale, the flow becomes turbulent, requiring a correction to Eq. (2.44). Chakrabarti [18] proposed the following form:

$$B_{F0} = 0.787\rho S r_e^2 \sqrt{\omega\nu} \left\{ 1 + 0.00814 \left(\frac{r_e^2 \phi_a^2 \omega}{\nu} \right)^{0.386} \right\} \quad (2.48)$$

Here, the first term represents the linear laminar component, while the second term accounts for turbulent correction. The correction increases with Reynolds number and roll amplitude.

Forward Speed Correction

Schmitke [30] suggested a forward-speed correction, as the friction component increases slightly with Froude number:

$$B_F = B_{F0} \left(1 + 4.1 \frac{U}{\omega L} \right) \quad (2.49)$$

This form is widely accepted for practical ship design, especially in predicting damping under realistic sailing conditions. Here, U is the forward speed and L is the ship length.

2.3.7 Hull Lift Component

Lift damping in roll generates a lift-induced moment, analogous to the lift force produced by a ship undergoing sway motion while advancing. Ikeda et al. [21] simplified this complex hydrodynamic phenomenon into an equivalent linear damping expression:

$$B_L = 0.075\rho ULD^3 k_N \left[1 - 2.8 \frac{OG}{D} + 4.667 \left(\frac{OG}{D} \right)^2 \right] \quad (2.50)$$

The coefficient k_N is defined as:

$$k_N = 2\pi \frac{D}{L} + \kappa \left(4.1 \frac{B}{L} - 0.045 \right) \quad (2.51)$$

The value of κ depends on C_M :

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} 0.0 & \text{for } C_M \leq 0.92 \\ 0.1 & \text{for } 0.92 \leq C_M \leq 0.97 \\ 0.3 & \text{for } 0.97 \leq C_M \leq 0.99 \end{cases} \quad (2.52)$$

Here, C_M represents the mid-ship cross-section coefficient. As mentioned above, the lift damping varies linearly with the ship's forward speed U and vanishes at zero speed. At high speeds, however, its contribution to the total roll damping becomes significant.

2.3.8 Eddy Making Component

At zero forward speed, the eddy-making component for a naked hull is mainly due to sectional vortices. For slender ships, the vortices are shed from the forward and the aft regions while for a vessel with a fuller shape the mid-ship region contributes significantly to the phenomenon.

Ikeda et.al [21] found from experiments on two-dimensional cylinders with various sections that this component for a naked hull is proportional to the square of both frequency and roll amplitude. The eddy damping per unit length for a cross-section is given by:

$$\frac{B_{E0}}{L} = \frac{4}{3\pi} D^4 \omega \phi_a C_R \quad (2.53)$$

C_R is defined as shown in Eq. (2.54) where M_{RE} represents the eddy damping moment.

$$C_R = \frac{M_{RE}}{\frac{1}{2}\rho D^4 L \dot{\theta} |\dot{\theta}|} \quad (2.54)$$

H_0 and σ represent half the beam-draft ratio and area coefficient at the underwater cross-section under consideration. The number of vortices shed from a section depends on these 2 parameters.

$$H_0 = \frac{B}{2D} \quad (2.55)$$

$$\sigma = \frac{A_{\text{sec}}}{BD} \quad (2.56)$$

The eddy damping moment M_{RE} is empirically estimated by

$$M_{RE} = \frac{1}{2}\rho L r_{\text{max}}^2 D^2 \dot{\theta} |\dot{\theta}| C_P \left\{ \left(1 - f_1 \frac{R_b}{D}\right) \left(1 - \frac{OG}{D}\right) + f_2 \left(H_0 - f_1 \frac{R_b}{D}\right)^2 \right\} \quad (2.57)$$

Where R_b is the bilge radius given by Eq. (2.58).

$$R_b = \begin{cases} 2D \sqrt{\frac{H_0(\sigma-1)}{\pi-4}} & \text{for } R_b < D, R < \frac{B}{2} \\ D & \text{for } H_0 \geq 1, \frac{R_b}{D} > 1 \\ \frac{B}{2} & \text{for } H_0 \leq 1, \frac{R_b}{D} > H_0 \end{cases} \quad (2.58)$$

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{2} [1 + \tanh(20(\sigma - 0.7))] \quad (2.59)$$

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos(\pi\sigma)) - 1.5 (1 - e^{-5(1-\sigma)}) \sin^2(\pi\sigma) \quad (2.60)$$

Ikeda et. al [20] assumed simple pressure distributions around the sections. The magnitude of the pressure coefficient C_p can be taken as a function of the maximum relative velocity to the mean velocity on the hull surface $\gamma = V_{\text{max}}/V_{\text{mean}}$. This can be approximated by using the potential flow theory.

$$C_p = \frac{1}{2} (0.87e^{-\gamma} - 4e^{-0.187\gamma} + 3) \quad (2.61)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} f_3}{2D \left(1 - \frac{OG}{D}\right) \sqrt{H'_0 \sigma'}} \left(r_{\text{max}} + \frac{2M_1}{H_1} \sqrt{A_1^2 + B_1^2} \right) \quad (2.62)$$

where $H'_0 = \frac{H_0}{1-OG/D}$ and $\sigma' = \frac{\sigma-OG/D}{1-OG/D}$.

$$f_3 = 1 + 4e^{-1.65 \times 10^5 (1-\sigma)^2} \quad (2.63)$$

$$A_1 = -2a_3 \cos(5\psi) + a_1(1 - a_3) \cos(3\psi) + \left\{ (6 - 3a_1)a_3^2 + (a_1^2 - 3a_1)a_3 + a_1^2 \right\} \cos(\psi)$$

$$B_1 = -2a_3 \sin(5\psi) + a_1(1 - a_3) \sin(3\psi) + \left\{ (6 + 3a_1)a_3^2 + (a_1^2 + 3a_1)a_3 + a_1^2 \right\} \sin(\psi)$$

$$H_1 = 1 + a_1^2 + 9a_3^2 + 2a_1(1 - 3a_3) \cos(2\psi) - 6a_3 \cos(4\psi)$$

$$M_1 = \frac{B}{2(1 + a_1 + a_3)}$$

(2.64)

$$r_{\max} = M_1 \sqrt{\left\{ (1 + a_1) \sin(\psi) - a_3 \sin(3\psi) \right\}^2 + \left\{ (1 - a_1) \cos(\psi) + a_3 \cos(3\psi) \right\}^2}$$

(2.65)

where:

$$\psi = \begin{cases} \psi_1 = 0 & \text{for } r_{\max}(\psi_1) \geq r_{\max}(\psi_2) \\ \psi_2 = \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{a_1(1+a_3)}{4a_3} \right) & \text{for } r_{\max}(\psi_1) < r_{\max}(\psi_2) \end{cases}$$

(2.66)

Here a_1, a_3 are Lewis form coefficients corresponding to the given hull shape. In this work, the following equations were used to evaluate them:

$$\alpha = \frac{H'_0 - 1}{H'_0 + 1}$$

$$\beta = \left(\frac{4\sigma'}{\pi} \right) (1 - \alpha^2) + \alpha^2$$

(2.67)

$$a_3 = \frac{-\beta + \sqrt{3 - 2\beta}}{\beta + 3}$$

$$a_1 = \alpha(1 + a_3)$$

For a 3-dimensional ship form, the above sectional coefficients are integrated over the length of the ship. Thus the section damping coefficient considers the section geometry of the ship along its length. The current code takes in the 3D form in .STL mesh format and extracts section data from it.

In the presence of steady forward speed, the eddy making damping decreases. Ikeda et al. [21] proposed the following empirical formula for an eddy-making damping coefficient in non-zero U ,

$$B_E = B_{E0} \left[\frac{(0.04\omega L/U)^2}{1 + (0.04\omega L/U)^2} \right] \quad (2.68)$$

2.3.9 Bilge Keel Component

The bilge keel is an effective and efficient means of increasing overall damping, thereby reducing excessive roll motion in ships and barges. When bilge keels are installed, they enhance damping through two primary mechanisms: the normal force acting on the keel itself and the pressure variations induced on the hull surface by their presence (Ikeda et al.[21]).

At larger roll angles, additional damping arises from the interaction of the bilge keels with the free surface. Furthermore, at forward speed, the lift effect generated by the bilge keels due to the effective angle of attack developed also contributes to improved roll damping performance (Ikeda et al.[24]).

Bilge keel damping can therefore be divided into 4 components:

$$B_{BK} = B_{BKN} + B_{BKH} + B_{BKW} + B_{BKL} \quad (2.69)$$

Bilge Keel Normal Force

The bilge keel normal force component represents a significant contribution to roll damping, resulting from drag forces generated as the bilge keels oscillate through the fluid. Following the formulation by Ikeda et al. [21], the bilge keel normal force component at zero forward speed per unit length, denoted as B'_{BKN0} , is expressed as:

$$B'_{BKN0} = \frac{8}{3\pi} \rho r^3 \omega \phi_a b_{BK} f^2 \left[22.5 \frac{b_{BK}}{\pi r \phi_a f} + 2.4 \right] \quad (2.70)$$

Here, b_{BK} is the bilge keel span, r is the distance from the roll axis to the bilge keel given by:

$$r = d \sqrt{\left\{ H_0 - \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\right) \frac{R}{d} \right\}^2 + \left\{ 1 - \frac{OG}{d} - \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\right) \frac{R}{d} \right\}^2} \quad (2.71)$$

where d is the sectional depth and R is the sectional bilge radius given by (2.58).

f is a correction factor to take into account the increment of flow velocity at the bilge, determined from the experiments as:

$$f = 1 + 0.3e^{-160(1-\sigma)} \quad (2.72)$$

The total bilge keel normal force damping component B_{BKN0} is obtained by integrating (2.70) along the length of the bilge keel.

Bilge Keel-Hull Interaction

The bilge keel-hull interaction component is another significant component that contributes to roll damping, arising from the pressure field modification on the hull surface induced by the presence of the bilge keel. Following the formulation by [23], this damping component B'_{BKH} per unit length is expressed as:

$$B'_{BKH0} = \frac{4}{3\pi} \rho r^2 f^2 \omega \phi_a \int_G C_p l_p dG \quad (2.73)$$

where l_p indicates the moment lever arm for the ship section. The integration is performed over the girth of the hull section. It is evaluated using the expression:

$$\int_G C_p l_p dG = d^2 (-A_0 C_p^- + B_0 C_p^+) \quad (2.74)$$

C_p^+ and C_p^- are pressure coefficients on the top and bottom of the bilge keel where it is attached to the hull surface. C_p^+ was determined empirically by Ikeda, et al. [23] based on model tests with conventional ships as 1.2

The drag coefficient, C_D , was based on a zero-speed formulation and empirical predictions using the KC number.

$$C_D = 22.5 \frac{b_{BK}}{\pi r \phi_a f} + 2.4 \quad (2.75)$$

and drag coefficient being the difference in the pressure coefficients on either side of the bilge keel, ie. $C_p^+ - C_p^-$,

$$C_p^- = -22.5 \frac{b_{BK}}{\pi r \phi_a f} - 1.2 \quad (2.76)$$

The coefficient A_0 and B_0 are given by:

$$A_0 = (m_3 + m_4)m_8 - m_7^2 \quad (2.77)$$

$$B_0 = \frac{m_4^3}{3(H_0 - 0.215m_1)} + \frac{(1 - m_1^2)(2m_3 - m_2)}{6(1 - 0.215m_1)} + (m_3m_5 + m_4m_6)m_1 \quad (2.78)$$

where:

$$m_1 = R/d$$

$$m_2 = OG/d$$

$$m_3 = 1 - m_1 - m_2$$

$$m_4 = H_0 - m_1 \quad (2.79)$$

$$m_5 = \frac{(0.414H_0 + 0.0651m_1^2 - (0.382H_0 + 0.0106)m_1)}{(H_0 - 0.215m_1)}(1 - 0.215m_1)$$

$$m_6 = \frac{(0.414H_0 + 0.0651m_1^2 - (0.382 + 0.0106H_0)m_1)}{(H_0 - 0.215m_1)}(1 - 0.215m_1)$$

$$m_8 = \begin{cases} m_7 + 0.414 \cdot m_1 & \text{if } S_0 > 0.25\pi R \\ m_7 + \sqrt{2} \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{S_0}{R}\right)\right) m_1 & \text{if } S_0 \leq 0.25\pi R \end{cases} \quad (2.80)$$

$$m_7 = \begin{cases} S_0/d - 0.25\pi \cdot m_1 & \text{if } S_0 > 0.25\pi R \\ 0 & \text{if } S_0 \leq 0.25\pi R \end{cases}$$

Here S_0 is the length of the negative pressure along the hull section, given by:

$$S_0 = 0.3 \frac{\pi r \phi_a f}{b_{BK}} + 1.95 \quad (2.81)$$

To predict the bilge keel component, the method assumes a simplified cross section consisting of a vertical side wall, a horizontal bottom, and a quarter-circle bilge radius. The bilge keel is placed at the midpoint of the arc, oriented perpendicular to the hull surface. These assumptions may lead to errors if the real cross-section has large differences from this assumed one. A more general method allowing user-defined bilge keel locations has not been implemented in the present work.

Bilge Keel Wave-Making

The wave-making component of bilge keel damping, denoted as B_{BKW} , is one of the more challenging aspects to quantify in roll damping analysis. This difficulty arises primarily from the complex phase relationship between the wave systems generated by the ship's hull and those created by the bilge keels themselves. Depending on their relative phases, these wave systems may combine constructively or destructively, leading to either increased or decreased overall damping effects (Ikeda et al.[23]; Himeno [25]).

For typical bilge keel configurations where the bilge keel span b_{BK} ranges between $B/60$ and $B/80$ of the ship's beam B , experimental studies by Himeno [25] suggest that the wave-making component can often be neglected. This approximation holds particularly for small roll amplitudes where the bilge keel's interaction with the free surface remains minimal, making its contribution relatively small compared to other damping components. However, Himeno notes important exceptions to this assumption, particularly for vessels with larger bilge keels such as naval ships, where the wave-making effects may become significant regardless of roll amplitude.

The bilge keel wave-making component increases substantially with larger roll amplitudes. As the roll angle grows, so does the bilge keel's penetration into and emergence from the water, leading to more pronounced free surface interactions and consequent wave-making effects. Bassler [27] developed a formulation to estimate the relative magnitude of this damping component across different ranges of roll amplitudes and oscillation frequencies. The formulation treats the bilge keel as a pulsating source operating at the roll frequency ω , with its effective depth relative to the free surface (d_{BK}) varying with roll amplitude ϕ .

The wave-making damping component is expressed as:

$$B_{BKW0} \approx C_{BK}(b_{BK}).exp \left[\frac{-\omega^2}{g} d_{BK}(\phi_a) \right] \quad (2.82)$$

where C_{BK} represents the source strength coefficient, dependent on the bilge keel span b_{BK} . For simplification, C_{BK} is approximated as the ratio b_{BK}/B , where B is the ship's beam. d_{BK} is the distance from the free surface to the bilge keel, given by:

$$d_{BK}(\phi) = r \left[\left(\frac{2D/B}{\sqrt{1 + (2D/B)^2}} \right) \cos \phi_a - \sin \phi_a \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + (2D/B)^2}} \right) \right] \quad (2.83)$$

The forward speed effects are taken into account by the correction originally proposed by Ikeda et al. [21] for the hull wave-damping component.

$$\frac{B_{44W}}{B_{44W0}} = 0.5 \cdot \left[\begin{array}{c} (A_2 + 1) + \\ (A_2 - 1) \cdot \tanh(20(\Omega - 0.3)) + \\ (2A_1 - A_2 - 1) \cdot \\ \exp\{-150 \cdot (\Omega - 0.25)^2\} \end{array} \right] \quad (2.84)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= 1 + \xi_d^{-1.2} e^{-2\xi_d} \\ A_2 &= 0.5 + \xi_d^{-1} e^{-2\xi_d} \end{aligned} \quad (2.85)$$

$$\xi_d = \frac{\omega^2 D}{g}, \quad \Omega = \frac{V\omega}{g}$$

Bilge Keel Lift

The influence of forward speed on the bilge keel damping component were assumed to be negligible in the previous sections. However, the lift force generated at higher speeds requires consideration. Modeling the bilge keel as a low-aspect-ratio wing, we apply Jones' theory (Ikeda et al. [24]) to analyze the combined flow effects:

$$\alpha = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{u}{U} \right), \quad V_r = \sqrt{U^2 + u^2} \quad (2.86)$$

where α is the effective angle of attack, V_r is the resultant flow velocity. U is the ship's forward speed. $u = r\dot{\phi}_a = r\omega\phi_a$ represents the tangential velocity from roll motion.

The lift force on a bilge keel is given by:

$$L_{BK} = \frac{\rho\pi\alpha V_r^2 b_{BK}^2}{2} \quad (2.87)$$

The corresponding roll damping coefficient becomes:

$$B_{BKL} = \frac{2L_{BK}r}{\phi_a\omega} \quad (2.88)$$

2.3.10 Calculation Procedure

The additional roll damping calculation module is integrated into the RAO calculation module of *seakeepy*. The RAO calculation incorporating additional roll damping can be performed in two distinct ways, as described below.

Method 1: RAO Database Generation

The first approach involves generating an RAO database for predefined vessel speeds and roll angles. The seakeeping module includes functionalities that allow for subsequent lookup operations within this database file to retrieve the RAO corresponding to a specific speed and roll angle as required. This method is useful for scenarios where precomputed data can significantly reduce computational overhead during runtime.

Method 2: Iterative RAO Calculation for Specific Sea States

The second method involves calculating the RAO for a specific sea state through an iterative process. This approach is necessary because the RAO and the equivalent damping are interdependent, as explained in section 2.3.3. The iteration proceeds as follows:

1. **Initialization:** The process begins by calculating the RAO using only the linear wave damping component. This initial step provides a preliminary estimate of the maximum response.
2. **Equivalent Damping Update:** The maximum response obtained from the initial calculation is used to derive a new equivalent damping value.
3. **Subsequent Iterations:** A new RAO calculation is performed using the updated equivalent damping value. This cycle of updating the damping and recalculating the RAO is repeated iteratively.
4. **Convergence Criterion:** The iteration continues until the solution converges. Convergence is determined based on the error in the standard deviation of the response spectrum $S(\omega_e)|H(w_e)|^2$ between two consecutive iterations. The standard deviation σ is computed as the square root of the variance σ^2 , where the variance is given by:

$$\sigma^2 = \int_0^{\infty} S(\omega_e)|H(w_e)|^2 d\omega_e$$

The convergence is achieved when the difference in the standard deviation between successive iterations falls below a predefined threshold (< 1%).

Figure 2.8 shows the flow chart explaining this process with some more details, like the input information and file types.

Figure 2.7: Flow chart of the Iterative RAO Calculation process

2.4 Aerodynamic Damping due to Wind-Assisted Propulsion Devices

Although the primary purpose of wind-assisted propulsion (WAP) device equipment on board is to harness wind energy, it is empirically known that it can also reduce vessel motion as a secondary effect. This occurs because the aerodynamic forces generated by the sails act to damp roll motion by altering the relative inflow speed and inflow angle induced by the vessel's motion.

With VPLP Design now developing multiple projects involving wind-assisted propulsion devices in the maritime sector, this is a topic that merits quantification in the early design phase. For example, the *Canopée* project [34] recently announced that its wingsails reduced fuel consumption by 15%, equivalent to approximately 3.5 tonnes of fuel per day at sea without affecting the vessel's speed. If the associated motion-damping benefits could be quantified, this could further increase the commercial attractiveness and accelerate the adoption of wind-assisted propulsion technologies in the industry.

Figure 2.8: The cargo ship *Canopée*, launched in late 2022, was designed to transport parts of the Ariane 6 rocket from European ports to French Guiana. The 121 m vessel is equipped with four 363 m² wingsails mounted on 36 m masts. (Photo Credits : Tom Van Oossanen)

This section describes the implementation of an aerodynamic motion-damping prediction tool in *seakeepy*, following the work of Johanna Tranell [33] on the same topic. Two WAP systems are considered: the Flettner rotor and the rigid wingsail. By including the roll and pitch rigid-body motions, the model captures the dynamic wind conditions acting on the WAP devices.

The Flettner rotor is modelled using empirical expressions derived from full-scale measurements on a vessel equipped with a single rotor. The wingsail model assumes linear foil theory and employs a lifting-line approach to calculate aerodynamic forces and the resulting damping. Dynamic lift effects due to oscillatory motion are neglected in this study. Although the aerodynamic model may overestimate or underestimate damping depending on the degree of freedom considered, it has been verified to provide reliable results over a selected range of true wind angles.

This model was chosen for its computational efficiency and ease of implementation. Tranell [33] provided reference code that served as the foundation for this work. The implementation in *seakeepy* was extended with additional capabilities, including the option to specify user-defined lift and drag coefficients, corrections to aerodynamic added mass coefficients, and the ability to estimate damping in irregular seas. The following sections provide a brief overview of the damping model and the author's contributions to its further development and integration into *seakeepy*.

2.4.1 Coordinate System

Tranell [33] introduces a drift angle between the coordinate systems $OXYZ$ and $oxyz$ to describe the aerodynamic model. In this framework, the wind model is defined in the flow-fixed $OXYZ$ coordinate system, while the sail models make use of both coordinate systems. Since the sails form the interface between the wind and the ship models, they are responsible for transforming the aerodynamic forces from the flow-fixed system into the ship-fixed system.

The true wind angle (TWA) is defined such that it is measured in the opposite direction to the wave heading. Figure 2.9 illustrates these modifications. Note that the drift angle is typically very small. In the figure, it is exaggerated for clarity.

Figure 2.9: Schematic of the modified coordinate systems (*Tranell [33]*)

2.4.2 Aerodynamic Damping Model

This section briefly introduces the work of Tranell [33] before presenting the author's contributions. The aerodynamic model assumes steady wind conditions without turbulence. The wind forces acting on the vessel do not excite its motion; instead, they contribute to a heel angle. Furthermore, the effects of interactions between the wind-assisted propulsion (WAP) devices and between the devices and the hull are neglected.

The ship motion was simplified to a 2-degree-of-freedom (DOF) system in pitch and roll, as these are the motions most affected by aerodynamic damping. However, Tranell [33] concludes that the damping effects on pitch motion are negligible.

Harmonic motion is imposed on the vessel in the roll and pitch DOFs, inducing apparent wind velocities V_R and V_P . V_{WS} is the apparent wind induced by the steady forward vessel speed. Figure 2.10 illustrates the wind velocity triangle acting on a given section of a WAP device. These velocities alter the apparent

Figure 2.10: The steady and dynamic wind velocity triangles, subject to the $OXYZ$ reference frame (*Tranell [33]*)

wind speed $V_{A,U}$ and the apparent wind angle AWA_U occurs at the frequency of the imposed harmonic motion. The imposed motions are given by:

$$\eta_4 = \eta_{4a} \cos(\omega_e t + \delta_4) \quad (2.89)$$

$$\eta_5 = \eta_{5a} \cos(\omega_e t + \delta_5) \quad (2.90)$$

where η_{4a}, η_{5a} are user defined roll and pitch amplitudes respectively. ω_e is the encounter frequency

Once the wind triangle information is obtained over a full period for all sections of a WAP device, the sectional lift and drag forces can be estimated using the following equations:

$$dL = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a C_L V_A^2 d, \quad (2.91)$$

$$dD = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a C_D V_A^2 d, \quad (2.92)$$

where ρ_a is the air density, d section diameter or chord, and C_L and C_D are the sectional lift and drag coefficients, respectively. Tranell [33] calculates these coefficients for Flettner rotors using empirical data from full-scale rotor measurements. For rigid wing sails, the coefficients are derived from linear theory, accounting for 3D effects under the assumption of an elliptical lift distribution. The work also discusses optional stall modeling, where the lift coefficient drops to a low value and the drag coefficient is assigned a high value if the angle of attack exceeds a defined threshold during oscillations.

The heeling and driving forces were computed from the sectional forces as:

$$dF_D = dL \sin(\text{AWA}) - dD \cos(\text{AWA}), \quad (2.93)$$

$$dF_H = dL \cos(\text{AWA}) + dD \sin(\text{AWA}). \quad (2.94)$$

Note that dF_H and dF_D are by definition along the (X, Y) inertial axes. These must be projected onto the (x, y) body-fixed axes where the rigid body motions are defined.

In the present work, the surge and sway forces are included in the aerodynamic added mass and damping calculations to provide a more complete treatment. These coefficients may play an important role in vessel dynamics, particularly for smaller vessels.

The sectional forces in surge, sway, roll and pitch directions are then:

$$dF_1 = -dF_H \sin \beta + dF_D \cos \beta, \quad (2.95)$$

$$dF_2 = -dF_H \cos \beta - dF_D \sin \beta, \quad (2.96)$$

$$dF_4 = -dF_H z \cos \beta - dF_D z \sin \beta, \quad (2.97)$$

$$dF_5 = -dF_H z \sin \beta + dF_D z \cos \beta. \quad (2.98)$$

Aerodynamic Added Mass Coefficients

The added mass formulation from [33] has been modified in two key aspects:

1. Inclusion of additional aerodynamic added mass coefficients for surge and sway motion
2. Introduction of a 3D correction coefficient in the added mass term

Tranell [33] employed strip theory to estimate added mass for WAP devices. This approach neglects three-dimensional effects by modeling the sail as a flat plate of equivalent planform, divided into strips with added mass calculated using potential flow theory (Figure 2.11).

The aerodynamic added mass coefficients are calculated as:

$$A_{22}^{\text{aero}} = \int_f^{f+P} \rho \frac{\pi}{4} c(z)^2 dz, \quad (2.99)$$

$$A_{42}^{\text{aero}} = \int_f^{f+P} \rho \frac{\pi}{4} c(z)^2 z dz, \quad (2.100)$$

$$A_{44}^{\text{aero}} = \int_f^{f+P} \rho \frac{\pi}{4} c(z)^2 z^2 dz. \quad (2.101)$$

Figure 2.11: Strip theory application to a rigid sail (*Gerhardt [35]*)

For rigid sails, surge added mass terms are typically neglected due to their minimal contribution in the sway direction. However, Flettner rotors require consideration of these terms, introducing three additional coefficients:

$$A_{11}^{\text{aero}}, \quad A_{51}^{\text{aero}}, \quad \text{and} \quad A_{55}^{\text{aero}}. \quad (2.102)$$

By symmetry, the following relationships hold:

$$A_{42}^{\text{aero}} = A_{24}^{\text{aero}}, \quad (2.103)$$

$$A_{51}^{\text{aero}} = A_{15}^{\text{aero}} \quad (2.104)$$

This formulation extends the original six added mass terms from [33] with six additional coefficients for a more comprehensive treatment.

Gerhardt [35] incorporated three-dimensional effects into the added mass coefficients by introducing a factor calculated from the difference between the added mass obtained from strip theory to the analytical solution for an ellipse having the same aspect ratio as the sail. Therefore,

$$A_{jk,corrected}^{\text{aero}} = A_{jk}^{\text{aero}} \cdot S(AR) \quad (2.105)$$

The factor S , a function of the aspect ratio, varies as shown in Fig. 2.12

The rigid wingsails analyzed in the latter part of this work have an aspect ratio of 3.5, resulting in about 30% reduction in the calculated added mass compared with the formulations of Tranell [33], which represents a substantial difference.

Figure 2.12: 3D Correction factor as a function of aspect ratio (adapted from Gerhardt [35])

Aerodynamic Damping Coefficients

The sectional forces given in Eqs. 2.95–2.98 are integrated along the span of the WAP devices to obtain the total forces acting on them over a period of oscillation. Tranell [33] found that these forces were predominantly sinusoidal, except in cases where stall occurred (particularly for wingsails). Furthermore, Tranell [33] fitted the forces with sinusoidal functions of the form:

$$F_{jk}^{\text{aero}} = a_{jk}^{\text{aero}} \sin(\omega_e t + \epsilon_k) + d_{jk}^{\text{aero}}, \quad (2.106)$$

where d_{jk}^{aero} is a constant mean value.

The aerodynamic damping coefficients were then obtained from the force derivatives as:

$$B_{jk}^{\text{aero}} = \frac{dF_{jk}}{d\dot{\eta}_k} = \frac{a_{jk}^{\text{aero}}}{\omega_e \eta_{ka}}. \quad (2.107)$$

Considering the surge and sway forces on the WAP devices, four additional aerodynamic damping coefficients, B_{41}^{aero} , B_{42}^{aero} , B_{51}^{aero} , and B_{52}^{aero} , are introduced in addition to the existing coefficients B_{44}^{aero} , B_{45}^{aero} , B_{55}^{aero} , and B_{54}^{aero} reported by Tranell [33].

2.4.3 Calculation Procedure

As discussed in section 2.3.10, The RAO calculation incorporating aerodynamic damping can be performed in two distinct ways, as described below:

Method 1: RAO Database Generation

If the expected roll and pitch motion amplitudes are provided, RAOs can be calculated based on the WAP device geometry and other input parameters. This is a straightforward process. The RAO calculation now includes the additional roll damping coefficient from the previous section, as well as all the aerodynamic coefficients introduced in this section. These contributions can be enabled or disabled individually at the user's discretion. Once calculated, an RAO database file is generated, allowing the user to retrieve the desired RAO values using the seakeeping module of *seakeepy*.

Method 2: Iterative RAO Calculation for Specific Sea States

One of the assumptions in Tranell [33] was that aerodynamic damping coefficients could be superimposed. This assumption does not hold when calculating responses for an irregular seastate, because the aerodynamic damping depends on the roll amplitude, which varies across the frequencies in the response spectrum. For coefficients to be linearly superimposable, they must be calculated for a unit wave amplitude, a condition that does not apply to the aerodynamic coefficients in question.

This issue was discussed earlier in Section 2.3.3, where a form of stochastic linearization was proposed to obtain effective damping values for a given seastate. The starting point is to assume that the aerodynamic damping varies nonlinearly with roll rate, as expressed by:

$$B^{\text{aero}}(\dot{\phi}) = B_1\dot{\phi} + B_2\dot{\phi}|\dot{\phi}| + B_3\dot{\phi}^3 \quad (2.108)$$

Here, B_1 , B_2 , and B_3 are coefficients describing the linear, quadratic, and cubic dependencies on roll rate $\dot{\phi}$, respectively.

Using the equivalent linearization approach for regular waves, the aerodynamic damping coefficient for a given encounter frequency ω_e and roll/pitch amplitude η_k can be expressed as:

$$B_{j,k}^{\text{aero}} = B_1 + \frac{8}{3\pi}B_2(\omega_e\eta_k) + \frac{3}{4}B_3(\omega_e\eta_k)^2 \quad (2.109)$$

This relationship allows the nonlinear damping model in Eq. (2.108) to be represented by an equivalent linear coefficient, $B_{j,k}^{\text{aero}}$, for a specific motion amplitude and frequency, which can already be calculated from Eq. 2.107.

For irregular seastates, the goal is to obtain an equivalent damping value that accounts for the statistical variation of roll velocity. Using stochastic linearization, the aerodynamic damping for a seastate is given by:

$$B_{j,k,\text{seastate}}^{\text{aero}} = B_1 + \sqrt{\frac{8}{\pi}}B_2\sigma_{\dot{x}} + 3B_3\sigma_{\dot{x}}^2 \quad (2.110)$$

where $\sigma_{\dot{x}}$ is the standard deviation of the roll/pitch velocity response. This form is analogous to Eq. (2.109), but with amplitude terms replaced by statistical measures derived from the response spectrum.

To determine the coefficients B_1 , B_2 , and B_3 , a regression fit can be performed using aerodynamic damping values computed for a range of encounter frequencies $\omega_{e,i}$ and their corresponding motion amplitudes $\eta_{k,i}$. These amplitudes can be obtained from:

$$\eta_{k,i} = \sqrt{S(\omega_{e,i}) |H_r(\omega_{e,i})|^2 \Delta\omega_e} \quad (2.111)$$

where $S(\omega_{e,i})$ is the encounter spectrum, $|H_r(\omega_{e,i})|$ is the relative motion response amplitude operator (RAO), and $\Delta\omega_e$ is the frequency interval.

By defining a new variable:

$$X = \omega_{e,i} \cdot \eta_{k,i} \quad (2.112)$$

Eq. (2.109) can be rewritten in the reduced form:

$$B_{j,k}^{\text{aero}} = B_1 + \frac{8}{3\pi} B_2 X + \frac{3}{4} B_3 X^2 \quad (2.113)$$

This reduction allows $B_{j,k}^{\text{aero}}$ to be expressed solely in terms of X , enabling the coefficients B_1 , B_2 , and B_3 to be efficiently recovered from a polynomial regression fit.

Figure 2.13: Regression curve fitted on aerodynamic roll damping values.

Once these coefficients are determined, Eq. (2.110) can be applied to compute the equivalent aerodynamic damping for the irregular seastate, using the statistical properties of the response. Figure 2.13 shows an example regression fit on aerodynamic roll damping values, B_{44}^{aero} . The simulation parameters used in this example are discussed later in Section 3.2. The regression curve demonstrates a reasonable agreement with the computed data.

Once the aerodynamic damping coefficients are estimated, the RAO for the given seastate can be calculated iteratively. In this process, the convergence criteria described in Section 2.3.10 are applied to both the roll and pitch responses. Fig 2.14 describes the flow of code for this calculation. An example of the damping configuration file is provided in Appendix I

Figure 2.14: Flow chart of the Iterative RAO Calculation process

Chapter 3

Results

This section presents the validation of the new features implemented in *seakeepy*. Following the code validation, a case study is conducted to demonstrate the performance of these features in a real-world scenario.

3.1 Code Validation

3.1.1 Slamming Analysis

This section compares the time-domain slamming analysis with the newly implemented frequency-domain slamming analysis. Obtaining experimental or numerical data for frequency-domain validation is challenging, as it requires both the amplitude and phase information of the vessel's motion, not just the RAO, as well as corresponding validation datasets. Such comprehensive data has proven difficult to acquire and could not be found in the existing literature. Consequently, this section focuses on examining how the frequency-domain results align with the theoretical factors affecting slamming and assessing their validity accordingly.

Figure 3.1: Underwater hull of catamaran model

For the following studies, a catamaran model was selected to investigate the influence of slamming occurrences at a given location. Two positions are examined: the bow of one of the demi-hulls and the wet deck. Table 3.1 below presents the main particulars of the vessel, along with the coordinates of the chosen positions.

Length	60 m
Breadth (overall)	22 m
Draft	3.7 m
Displacement	1448000 kg
Location of Demi-Hull Bow (x, y, z)	(30, 7.5, -3.7)
Location of Wet Deck (x, y, z)	(0, 0, 2.5)

Table 3.1: Particulars of the catamaran model

Two different sea states were considered in the analysis. The first corresponds to a moderate condition ($H_s = 4$ m, $T_p = 10$ s), and the second to a strong condition ($H_s = 7$ m, $T_p = 12$ s). Both cases were evaluated at two different vessel speeds (10, 15 knots) speeds and for wave headings ranging from 0° (following seas) to 180° (head seas). This approach provides a comprehensive assessment of how the results vary under different operating and environmental conditions.

(a) Position: Bow, Speed: 10 knots

(b) Position: Wet deck, Speed: 10 knots

(c) Position: Bow, Speed: 15 knots

(d) Position: Wet deck, Speed: 15 knots

Figure 3.2: No, of slamming occurrences vs wave heading for the moderate sea state ($H_s = 4$ m, $T_p = 10$ s)

The results present the number of slamming occurrences at a given location for different wave headings over a one-hour period, modelled using both the time-domain and frequency-domain approaches.

Both methodologies generally align with the factors affecting slamming discussed in Section 2.2.2. The influence of sea state severity is particularly evident when comparing Figs. 3.2 and 3.3, where the more severe sea state in Fig. 3.3 demonstrates significantly higher slamming occurrences.

The effect of heading angle further supports these findings, with slamming occurrences rapidly diminishing below 120° heading (more than 30° off the bow). The impact of draft is demonstrated by comparing bow and wet deck results. The wet deck, positioned 2.5 m above the waterline, experiences nearly negligible slamming events, as expected.

(a) Position: Bow, Speed: 10 knots

(b) Position: Wet deck, Speed: 10 knots

(c) Position: Bow, Speed: 15 knots

(d) Position: Wet deck, Speed: 15 knots

Figure 3.3: No. of slamming occurrences vs wave heading for the strong sea state ($H_s = 7$ m, $T_p = 12$ s)

The results from the time-domain and frequency-domain analyses show good agreement at lower speeds for both sea states. However, discrepancies become evident at higher speeds, likely due to the inherent differences in the modelling approaches. The frequency-domain method provides a more elegant treatment of an inherently non-linear phenomenon such as slamming by modelling it statisti-

cally, whereas the time-domain method, although more direct, suffers from the disadvantages discussed in Section 2.2.3.

In terms of computational efficiency, the frequency-domain method offers a clear advantage. For a single sea state, the time-domain approach required an average of 42 seconds to process all seven headings from 90° to 180° , whereas the frequency-domain results were obtained almost instantaneously. This computational benefit becomes particularly significant when performing criteria checks that require sweeping the entire scatter diagram.

Considering the agreement in results with theory, combined with its efficiency and practical applicability, the newly implemented frequency-domain approach can be regarded as superior to the existing time-domain method.

3.1.2 Additional Roll Damping

Monohulls

Validation of the additional roll-damping features primarily relies on numerical studies previously conducted on the same topic. Since the different components of roll damping cannot be isolated in practice, this study draws upon these numerical results for verification.

Figure 3.4: Underwater hull of the KVLCC2 model

The vessel selected for validation is a scaled model of the KVLCC2 tanker. The KVLCC2 [31] is the second variant of the MOERI tanker, featuring more U-shaped stern frame lines. This tanker model was chosen because it represents a conventional hull form with wall-sided sections, the type of vessel for which the component-based roll-damping method was developed. The principal particulars of the model are given in Table 3.2.

The results from the study by Alexandersson et al. [32] are used for code verification. In their work, the authors propose a hybrid method in which viscous roll damping from Ikeda's semi-empirical method is incorporated into an existing

LBP	4.706 m
Breadth	0.853 m
Draft	0.306 m
Displacement	0.993 m ³
VCG	0.274 m

Table 3.2: Principal particulars of the KVLCC2 model

three-dimensional, unsteady, fully nonlinear potential flow (FNPF) framework. A comparison of the eddy, lift, and friction damping obtained from the present code with those reported in their study is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Comparison of eddy, lift, and friction damping obtained from the present code with those reported in Alexandersson et al. [32]

The markers in the plot are the validation data points and the solid lines are the outputs of the current code. This case corresponds to a simulation of a roll decay test, with the vessel moving at a full-scale speed of 15 knots and a roll frequency of 2.48 rad/s.

The results show reasonable agreement, with a slight deviation observed in the eddy damping component. This deviation may be attributed to the complex formulation of eddy damping, which accounts for the vessel's geometry. It is worth noting that the published sources on component-based roll damping show slight variations from one another, primarily due to formulation errors or minor corrections introduced through proprietary experiments and validations.

Bilge Keels

Since no validation data were available for an openly accessible model with correctly defined parameters and all roll-damping components represented as in this study, a more approximate approach was adopted. Specifically, a visual inspection was carried out to compare the relative contributions of each component to the total roll damping of a vessel.

For this comparison, the KVLCC2 model discussed above was fitted with a bilge keel of length $LBP/2$ and a span equal to 2% of the vessel's breadth. The vessel speed and roll frequency are the same as in the last case. The results were compared to those reported by Himeno [25], where similar calculations were performed for an unspecified, yet still conventional, hull form.

Figure 3.6: Contribution of different roll damping components - Results from the present code

Figure 3.6 presents the results from the present code, while Figure 3.7 shows the corresponding results from the reference study. The relative contributions of the damping components appear to be consistent between the two cases. It should be noted that the linear wave damping contribution, B_{44W} , has not been included in Figure 3.6 as it is a potential flow contribution. This omission results in the bilge keel wave damping component, B_{44BKW} , having an almost negligible contribution, which in turn obscures the hull lift damping component, B_{44L} .

Additionally, the bilge keel-hull interaction component, B_{44BKH} , appears to contribute a higher proportion of the total damping in the present results compared to the reference. This difference may be attributed to variations in the parameters used in the two cases. Nevertheless, considering the complex formulations involved in the bilge keel damping components, the overall agreement is reasonable and the results are sufficiently accurate for practical applications.

Figure 3.7: Contribution of different roll damping components - Results from Himeno [25]

3.1.3 Aerodynamic Damping

Since the base code for aerodynamic damping was adapted from Tranell [33], the same validation results apply here as well.

For further details on the aerodynamic code validation, refer to Chapter 5 of Tranell [33], where the author compares the thrust coefficient of a single sail and a Flettner rotor to the corresponding CFD results. Additionally, the damping coefficients are compared against their analytical counterparts.

3.2 Case Study

This section presents a case study to assess the influence of the newly implemented features, specifically the additional roll damping and the damping contribution of wind-assisted propulsion (WAP) devices on vessel motion characteristics. The focus is on the damping performance provided by the WAP devices.

For the study, the KVLCC2 tanker was selected, as tankers typically have long, wide, open decks with relatively few tall structures compared to container ships or passenger vessels. The superstructure is generally located aft, leaving the forward and midship decks clear for installing large devices such as Flettner rotors, rigid sails, or suction wings, without interfering with cargo operations. Moreover, the conventional hull form allows for accurate prediction of additional roll damping effects, as demonstrated in the previous section.

The principal particulars of the KVLCC2 at full scale are listed in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3: Principal particulars of the KVLCC2 full-scale model.

Length Overall (LOA)	332 m
Length Between Perpendiculars (LBP)	320 m
Breadth	58 m
Draft	20.8 m
Freeboard	9.2 m
Vertical Center of Gravity (VCG)	18.9 m
Displacement	312,622 m ³
Block Coefficient (C_B)	0.8098
Midship Coefficient (C_M)	0.998

Eight rigid, rectangular wingsails of dimensions 35 m \times 10 m (aspect ratio 3.5) were installed on deck in the arrangement shown in Figure 3.8. Along the vessel length, the sails are spaced 60 m apart, with the aft-most sail 80 m forward of the stern and the forward-most sail 40 m aft of the bow. Transversely, they are placed 43 m apart, leaving a 7.5 m clearance from the side railings.

Figure 3.8: Top-down schematic showing the location of wingsails on the KVLCC2 tanker.

The model was analyzed under three environmental conditions, corresponding to sea states associated with Beaufort scale 4, 6, and 8. For all cases, the ship speed was kept constant at 20 knots, with wind and wave directions assumed to be aligned. Seven wave headings, ranging from 0° (head seas) to 180° (following seas), were considered for each case. The angle of attack of all sails was set to a moderate 10° . The details of the analyzed cases are summarized in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Environmental Parameters for the different cases

Sea State	Hs	Tp	True Wind Speed at 10m above MSL	Forward Speed
1	1.5 m	8 s	3 m/s	20 kn
2	4 m	10 s	11 m/s	20 kn
3	7 m	12 s	18 m/s	20 kn

The case study focuses on the roll motion for further analysis, as it has already been shown in Tranell [33] that aerodynamic pitch damping is minimal. This also enables a more straightforward comparison between the effects of additional roll damping and aerodynamic roll damping.

Response Amplitude Operators (RAOs) were computed for three sea states under different configurations:

1. No additional roll damping, no sails
2. Additional roll damping, no sails
3. Additional roll damping with sails

The figures 3.9 - 3.11 present the RAO values at the resonant frequencies for these cases.

Figure 3.9: Roll RAO values at the resonant frequencies for sea state 1

Figure 3.10: Roll RAO values at the resonant frequencies for sea state 2

Figure 3.11: Roll RAO values at the resonant frequencies for sea state 3

The inset graphs illustrate the comparison of RAO values with both damping modules turned off. The larger graphs provide a clearer comparison of the RAO values for the cases without sails and with sails. The presence of sails clearly contributes to a reduction of the peak values.

To better understand the damping characteristics of the sails, the resonant RAO values of the case with sails were compared across the three sea states. Fig. 3.12 shows these results

Interestingly, Sea State 1 shows lower peak RAO values than the more severe

Figure 3.12: Roll RAO values at the resonant frequencies for the case with sail for different sea states

Sea State 2, particularly for wave headings below 90 degrees. This further raises questions about how the damping values vary with wave heading across different sea states. The results are shown in Fig. 3.13

(a) Aerodynamic roll damping values for different sea states

(b) Additional roll damping values for different sea states

Figure 3.13: Components of roll damping for different sea states

The additional roll damping values increase with sea state severity across all wave heading angles. In contrast, the aerodynamic roll damping values exhibit a different behavior. For wave headings below 90°, the less severe Sea State 1 shows higher damping compared to the more severe Sea State 2 3

This observation is consistent with Tranell [33], who reported a conflict between thrust and damping values for wave headings below 90° (or true wind angles above 90°). As thrust increases with higher wind speeds, the damping values decrease. The trend observed here aligns with this description and explains the discrepancy

in the resonant RAO values shown in Fig. 3.12.

Finally, the percentage reduction in roll response peaks was compared across the different sea states and wave headings. This analysis was carried out to quantify the roll-damping effect of the rigid wing sails. The results are presented in Fig. 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Percentage of roll reduction between the cases with and without sails for the three sea states.

The plots of roll response reduction exhibit a similar trend across all sea states, except for Sea State 1 where the effect is very limited. In head and following seas, the roll reduction is negligible, whereas the maximum effect occurs in beam seas. In Sea State 3, the vessel experiences the largest reduction in roll response, of about 5.6% in beam seas, while in Sea State 2 the reduction is approximately 2.5%. In contrast, the sails have hardly any damping effect in Sea State 1.

Although the primary function of the sails is propulsion, this secondary and non-negligible reduction of roll motion, particularly in rougher beam seas, represents an added operational advantage.

Chapter 4

Conclusion & Future Work

This work focused on the development of the frequency-domain sea-keeping tool *seakeepy*, addressing several key aspects: the inclusion of forward-speed capabilities, implementation of a frequency-domain slamming subroutine, incorporation of additional roll-damping mechanisms, and the development of an aerodynamic damping module to quantify the motion-damping effects of wing-assisted propulsion (WAP) devices.

The proposed frequency-domain slamming method was demonstrated to be an improvement over the conventional time-series approach in several respects. The results were qualitatively validated; however, the author recommends further validation once suitable datasets become available.

The additional roll-damping subpackage introduced the much-needed non-potential roll-damping capabilities into *seakeepy*. This was achieved through Ikeda's component-based roll-damping formulation. The relevant theoretical background and implementation details were presented in a comprehensive manner, thereby providing a reference framework for further development. Capabilities were implemented to compute RAOs accounting for the additional roll damping, including the generation of RAO databases for both predefined roll angles and irregular sea states through stochastic linearization of the nonlinear roll-damping function.

Validation of the roll-damping submodule was carried out using the KVLCC2 tanker model. The computed damping components showed reasonable agreement with available references. In particular, the bilge keel damping contribution was qualitatively compared with results from the literature. Nevertheless, further validation is strongly recommended, especially for cases where additional experimental or numerical data may become available.

The aerodynamic damping model, based on the work of Tranell [33], provided a computationally efficient approach to quantify the motion-damping effects of WAP devices. Several improvements were introduced compared to existing work, such as the inclusion of aerodynamic added mass and damping in sway and surge degrees of freedom, refinement of aerodynamic added-mass coefficients through a three-dimensional correction factor, and the extension of the methodology to

irregular sea states.

A case study was performed with a full-scale KVLCC2 tanker equipped with eight rigid wing sails under a variety of operating conditions, providing practical estimates of the motion-damping capabilities of WAP devices. The results demonstrated that the sails introduced a non-negligible reduction in motion amplitudes, particularly in beam seas. The damping effect was observed to increase with sea-state severity, highlighting the potential benefits of integrating WAP devices in heavy weather conditions.

The introduction of new features in *seakeepy*, particularly the roll-damping and aerodynamic-damping submodules, has expanded the tool's capabilities but also introduced additional variables that must be calibrated to achieve reliable results. Due to time limitations, a thorough investigation of all parameter sensitivities and their implications could not be completed in the present work. The author therefore recommends systematic future studies to perform extensive validation of both slamming and roll-damping formulations against experimental and numerical benchmarks and to investigate parameter sensitivities within the roll-damping and aerodynamic submodules to ensure robustness of predictions.

In summary, this work has significantly advanced the frequency-domain capabilities of *seakeepy* by addressing critical gaps that previously prevented it from being considered a state-of-the-art tool, while also laying a strong foundation for future research and practical applications.

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Appendix I

Configuration File

```
1 {
2 //***** ADDITIONAL ROLL DAMPING - PARAMETERS *****
3 "USE_ADD": "Y", // Include Additional Roll Damping: "
4 "HULL_TYPE": "mono", // "mono" = Mono Hull, "cata" =
5 Catamaran, "tri" = Trimaran
6
7 //***** MAIN HULL CONFIGURATION *****
8 "L": 320, // Length between perpendiculars (m)
9 "B": 58.0, // Beam overall (m)
10 "D": 20.8, // Draft (m)
11 "VCG": 18.9, // Vertical center of gravity from
12 keel (m)
13 "CB": 0.8098, // Block coefficient
14 "CM": 0.998, // Midship coefficient
15
16 //***** INERTIA AND STIFFNESS MATRICES *****
17 "INERTIA_MATRIX": [
18 [3.20437550e+08, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, -0.00000000e
19 +00, -7.17780112e+08, -0.00000000e+00],
20 [0.00000000e+00, 3.20437550e+08, 0.00000000e+00, 7.17780112e
21 +08, -0.00000000e+00, 3.55685680e+09],
22 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 3.20437550e+08, 0.00000000e
23 +00, -3.55685680e+09, -0.00000000e+00],
24 [0.00000000e+00, 7.17780112e+08, 0.00000000e+00, 1.72000000e
25 +11, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
26 [-7.17780112e+08, 0.00000000e+00, -3.55685680e+09, 0.00000000e
27 +00, 2.05000000e+12, 0.00000000e+00],
28 [-0.00000000e+00, 3.55685680e+09, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e
29 +00, 0.00000000e+00, 2.05000000e+12]
30 ],
31
32 "STIFFNESS_MATRIX": [
33 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e
34 +00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
35 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e
36 +00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00],
37 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 1.68329452e+08, 3.64283665e
38 -07, 1.45263011e+09, 0.00000000e+00],
39 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 3.64283665e-07, 1.81925029e
40 +10, -2.34117033e-06, 0.00000000e+00],
```

```

29 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 1.45263011e+09, -2.34117033e
-06, 1.20504150e+12, 0.00000000e+00],
30 [0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e
+00, 0.00000000e+00, 0.00000000e+00]
31 ],
32
33 //***** AERODYNAMIC DAMPING PARAMETERS *****/
34 "USE_AEROD": "Y", // Include aerodynamic damping
35 "WAP_TYPE": 2, // 1 = Flettner Rotor, 2 = Sail
36 "INPUT_TYPE": "auto", // Coefficient calculation method
37 "INC_STALL": "Y", // Include stall effects
38 "ABL": "Y", // Include atmospheric boundary layer
39
40 //***** ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONS *****/
41 "TWS10": 18, // True wind speed at 10m (m/s)
42 "TWA10": 30, // True wind angle (deg)
43 "DRIFT_DEG": 5, // Vessel drift angle (deg)
44
45 //***** WAP CONFIGURATION *****/
46 "NUM_WAPS": 8, // Number of WAP devices
47 "WAP_LOCATIONS": [ // Device positions [x,y] in meters
48 [-80, -21.5], [-80, 21.5],
49 [-20, -21.5], [-20, 21.5],
50 [40, -21.5], [40, 21.5],
51 [100, -21.5], [100, 21.5]
52 ],
53 "WAP_AoA_SR": [10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10], // Angle of
attack/spin ratio
54 "WAP_BASE": 9.2, // WAP base height above MWL (m)
55
56 //***** FILE PATHS *****/
57 "GEOMETRY_FILE": "./KVLCC2_FULL.stl",
58 "NEMOH_FILE": "./KVLCC2_HALF_TRANSL.csv",
59 "WAP_GEOMETRY": "./geometry_sail.csv"
60 }

```

Listing 4.1: Example configuration file used for the case study